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The NLRP2 inflammasome functions in a nuclear transcriptional network.

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We recently described stage- and cell type-specific expression of NLRP2 in the human hematopoietic stem cell (HSC). We describe here a function of the NLRP2 innate immune sensor in a nuclear transcriptional network that involved the function of the RNA interference machinery (*DROSHA*), the DNA methyltransferase *DNMT1*, the non-coding RNA Xist and a molecule recently identified as regulating the activation or repression of Xist in response to induction DNA damage, MDC1.

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Results

NLRP2 functions in concert with a network of nuclear factors and machinery functioning in gene silencing and gene regulation.

